

Effect of Different Concentrations of Fungal Filtrate from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* on the Life Performance of *Aphis fabae* (Hemiptera: *Aphididae*)

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Suggested Citation

Al Ouboodi, A.S.Y., & Mohammed, A.A. (2024). Effect of Different Concentrations of Fungal Filtrate from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* on the Life Performance of *Aphis fabae* (Hemiptera: *Aphididae*). *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 1016-1027.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).85](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).85)

Abstract:

This study was conducted to assess the influence of different concentrations of fungal filtrate from *Amesia cymbiformis* and *Acrophialophora jodhpurensis* on the life performance of the *Aphis fabae*, including adult and nymph mortality rates. Additionally, the impact on adult productivity was assessed. Four different concentrations of the fungal filtrate (25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%) were employed for both fungi. The results demonstrated substantial differences in mortality rates associated to the concentration of fungal filtrate from both *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis*. The 100% concentration had the highest adult mortality rates, reaching 75% and 69%, respectively. The 100% concentration of *A. cymbiformis* fungal filtrate

had in the highest mortality rate for first nymphal stages at 82%, followed by second nymphal stages at 79.46%. The third and fourth nymphs showed mortality rates of 73.94% and 71%, respectively. Similarly, the 100% concentration of *A. jodhpurensis* fungal filtrate caused in the highest mortality rate for first nymphal stages at 82.5%, with second, third, and fourth nymphs stage displaying mortality rates of 78%, 74.6%, and 71.5%, respectively. The study also found a significant impact on the lowering of adult productivity. The average number of nymphal stages produced by adult *A. fabae* aphids using a 75% concentration of fungal filtrates from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* was 1.64 and 1.7 nymphs/female, respectively, compared to the control treatment, which showed an average of 3.82 nymphs/female after 5 days.

Keywords: *Amesia cymbiformis*, *Acrophialophora jodhpurensis*, *Aphis fabae*.

Introduction

The black bean aphid, *A. fabae*, has been identified as one of the globe's most serious agricultural pests (Esmaceli-Vardanjani et al., 2013). According to (Łukasik et al., 2022), this pest causes a significant threat to agricultural and ornamental plants. *A. fabae* is one of the 14 most important aphid species for agriculture (Meradsi

& Laamari, 2016). This aphid is polyphagous, alternating between primary and secondary host plants at different times of the year. Aphids often produce two sorts of damage. Skovgård and Stoddard (2023) observed that the huge amounts of sap extracted by these insects might induce plant weakness and wilting, following in significant production losses. Indirect damage occurs when honeydew is secreted on plants,

reducing photosynthetic efficiency (Nordey et al., 2021; Shannag, 2007). *A. fabae* is also a vector for viral infections in plants (Gadhav et al., 2020).

Entomopathogenic fungi are natural arthropod enemies and have been studied as potential biological control agents (Saruhan et al., 2014). Because of their extensive host range, about 1,000 species of entomopathogenic fungi play an important role in the biological control of numerous insect species. Aphids, thrips, whiteflies, mealybugs, and weevils are among the examples (Altinok et al., 2019; Gryganskyi et al., 2022; Kidanu & Hagos, 2020). These fungi are ecologically beneficial, naturally occurring, and harmless to the environment. They are also less hazardous to mammals and can be used in place of chemical pesticides, which insects find more difficult to resist (Batta, 2018; Rumbos & Athanassiou, 2017). The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of fungal filtrates from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* on the black bean aphid's life performance indicators.

Materials and Methods

Collection and Rearing of the Insect *Aphis fabae*, usually known as the black bean aphid, was collected from faba bean fields in Najaf Governorate for laboratory rearing. The identification of the insect was achieved by Associate Professor Dr. Akram Ali Muhammad from the Department of Plant Protection at the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kufa, Iraq. The insects were raised in four rectangular wooden cages of 100 cm × 50 cm each.

Preparation of several nymphal and adult stages of the insect Several stages of the *Aphis fabae*, including different nymphal and adults, were prepared. Fifteen adult aphids were transferred from the permanent colony to healthy faba bean leaves, with three adults/ leaf, via a sterile soft brush. To prevent the aphids from moving to other parts of the plant, clip cages were used (Mohammed, 2023). After 24 hours, the leaves were examined to confirm the presence of first nymphs. The adults were then removed from the plants using a soft brush. The infested plants

were maintained under laboratory conditions. To obtain nymphs of similar ages, first nymphs were reared for 2 days to obtain second nymphs. The nymphs were left for 4, 5.5, and 8 days to obtain third and fourth nymphs, and adults, correspondingly (Tsitsipis & Mittler, 1976)

Preparation of Different Concentrations of Fungal Filtrate The liquid media PDB (Potato Dextrose Broth) was prepared. Four 250 ml glass flasks containing 150 ml of PDB each were inoculated with three 0.5 cm diameter discs of pure fungal colonies of *A. jodhpurensis* and *A. cymbiformis* that had aged for seven days. Flasks were incubated at 25±2°C for 28 days, shaking every 2-3 days to promote even fungal growth. Subsequent incubation, the medium was filtered using Whatman No.1 filter paper, and the filtrate was passed through a 0.45-micron Millipore filter. The filtrates were collected in sterile glass flasks and kept chilled until needed (Melo et al., 2011). To determine the effects on insect mortality and adult productivity, different concentrations of the filtrates (25, 50, 75, and 100%) were prepared by diluting them with sterile distilled water.

Effect of Fungal Filtrates on Adult Mortality of *A. fabae* Adult *A. fabae* were prepared at two days old, with ten adults per replicate and four replicates. *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* fungal filtrates were generated at different concentrations (25, 50, 75, and 100%). Using a hand sprayer, adults were sprayed with 2 ml of fungal filtrate. Adults were sprayed with 2 mL of sterile distilled water as a control. Adult mortality rates were assessed after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 days.

Effect of Fungal Filtrates on Nymphal Mortality of *A. fabae* First instar nymphs and other nymphal stages were prepared, with 10 nymphs per replicate and four replicates. Fungal filtrate concentrations (25, 50, 75, 100%) of *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* were prepared separately. Nymphs were sprayed with 2 ml of the fungal filtrate using a hand sprayer. The control treatment consisted of nymphs sprayed with 2 ml of sterile distilled water. Mortality rates of the nymphs were recorded after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 days

Effect of Fungal Filtrates on Adult Productivity of *A. fabae* Adults aged 2 days of *A. fabae* were prepared, with one adult per replicate and ten replicates. Fungal filtrate concentrations (75%) of *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* were prepared. Adults were treated as described previously. The control treatment consisted of adults sprayed with 2 ml of sterile distilled water. The number of nymphs produced by the adults was recorded after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 days.

Statistical Analysis Results were analyzed using the GenStat statistical software (version 12). The LSD test at a 5% significance level was used to compare the means. Mortality rates were corrected using Abbott's Formula (Abbott, 1987), now known as the Schneider and Orell Formula. The corrected mortality percentage was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Corrected Mortality Percentage} = \frac{\text{Mortality in Control Mortality in Treatment} - \text{Mortality in Control}}{100 - \text{Mortality in Control}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Results and Discussion

Study on the Effect of the Fungal Filtrate of *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* on the Mortality Percentage of *A. fabae*

Table 1 shows the effects of different concentrations of *A. cymbiformis* fungal filtrate and time periods on the adjusted mortality percentages of *A. fabae* adults. The results revealed substantial differences in mortality rates determined by the concentration effect of the fungal filtrate. The 100% concentration resulted in the greatest mortality rate of 75%, whereas

concentrations of 25%, 50%, and 75% resulted in mortality rates of 26%, 50.5%, and 61%, respectively. In terms of time duration, the 5-day period performed considerably better than the other time periods, with a mortality rate of 57.5% compared to the 1, 2, and 3-day periods, which had corrected mortality percentages of 15%, 29.5%, and 44%, respectively. Regarding the interaction effect, the 100% concentration caused the highest mortality rate for *A. fabae* adults, reaching 100% after 4 days of treatment, significantly surpassing the other filtrate concentrations. After five days, the control treatment had a mortality rate of 2.5%.

Table 1. Effect of Different Concentrations of the Fungal Filtrate of *A. cymbiformis* and Time Periods on the Corrected Mortality Percentages of *A. fabae* Adults

Stage	Fungus type	Concentration%	Time period (Day)					Average effect of concentration
			1	2	3	4	5	
Adults	<i>A. cymbiformis</i>	%25	0	13	25	37.5	55	26
		%50	20	33	47.5	65	87.5	50.5
		%75	22.5	40	60	82.5	100	61.5
		%100	30	60	85	100	100	75
Average time effect			15	29.5	44	57.5	69	
L.S.D 0.05			Concentration effect		Time	Interaction		
			3.79		4.08	6.22		

Table 2 illustrates the effects of different concentrations of fungal filtrate from *A. jodhpurensis* and time periods on the adjusted mortality percentages of adult *A. fabae*. The results showed significant differences in

mortality rates based on fungal filtrate concentration. The 100% concentration had the greatest mortality rate of 69%, whereas the concentrations (25%, 50%, 75%) had mortality rates of 31%, 48%, and 62%, respectively. In

terms of time, the 5-day period performed considerably better than the other time periods, with a corrected mortality percentage of 100%, compared to the 1-, 2-, 3-, and 4-day periods, which had corrected mortality percentages of 12%, 27%, 42.5%, and 59%. The interaction

effect showed that concentrations of 75% and 100% caused the highest mortality rates for adult *A. fabae*, with 100% after 5 days of treatment. This was much higher than the other filtrate concentrations. The mortality rate for the control treatment was 2.5% after 5 days.

Table 2. Effect of Different Concentrations of *A. jodhpurensis* Fungal Filtrate and Time Periods on Corrected Percentages of *A. fabae* Adult Mortality

Stage	Fungus type	Concentration%	Timeperiod(Day)					Average effect of concentration
			1	2	3	4	5	
Adults	<i>A. jodhpurensis</i>	%25	0	10	25	48	72.5	31
		%50	12.5	30	48	65	85	48
		%75	22.5	43	63	83	100	62
		%100	25	50	75	98	100	69.5
Average time effect			12	27	43	59	72	
L.S.D 0.05			Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
			5.01		4.68		7.2929	

The current study showed that the fungal filtrates of *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* had a significant impact on the *A. fabae* adult. These results were agreed with of Hussain and Rashid (2007), who observed that *B. bassiana* had a significant effect on *A. fabae* adults, with the 100% concentration causing the highest mortality rate of 54.10%. This is due to the increased concentration of fungal filtrates, which leads to a greater accumulation of harmful compounds in insect cells, resulting in higher mortality rates. Male et al. (2009) showed that *M. anisopliae* can produce serious secondary metabolic products known as Destruxins. Berestetskiy and Hu (2021) discovered that wax moth larvae treated with modest quantities of Destruxins developed paralysis and died of their heart muscles. The capacity of fungus to connect to the body surface of insects and recognize their host is what causes its effects. The fungus utilizes its existing processes to break through the insect's body wall and into the internal cavity (Pedrini, 2022). When the fungus enters this nutrient-rich environment, its mycelium transforms into a specialized yeast-like cell phenotype known in invertebrate pathology as fungal filament bodies or blastospores. At this stage, the insect host's chances of surviving the

fungal infection are weak, despite the activation of its immune response (both cellular and humoral) in a final attempt to destroy the pathogenic fungus. Insects protect themselves from diseases by utilizing intricate and sophisticated innate immunity via cellular and humoral responses (Cooper & Eleftherianos, 2017; VELEZ, 2016).

Effect of Fungal Filtrate of *A.cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* on the Mortality Rates of Different Nymphal Stages of *A. fabae*

Table 3. shows the effects of the *A. cymbiformis* fungal filtrate at a 25% concentration, the targeted stage, and the time periods on the adjusted mortality rates of the *A. fabae* insect. The results revealed substantial differences in mortality rates according to the impact rate of the stage factor. The first nymphal stage had the highest mortality rate (63.5%), followed by the second nymphal stage (61.5%). The third and fourth nymphal stages had death rates of 51.5% and 41%, respectively. In terms of the impact of time period, the 5-day period outperformed the other time periods, achieving 69.46% compared to the time periods of 1, 2, 3, and 4 days, which yielded corrected mortality rates of 8%, 28%, 50.5%, and 63%, respectively. In terms of the

interaction impact, the first nymphal stage had the greatest death rate of 95% after 5 days, exceeding all other nymphal stages. Notably, the

control treatment resulted in a 1.5% death rate after five days.

Table 3. Effect of *A. cymbiformis* Fungal Filtrate at 25% Concentration on Corrected Mortality Percentages of Different Nymphal Stages of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	15	40	77.5	90	95	63.5
Second nymph	12.5	45	75	87.5	87.5	61.5
Third nymph	7.5	73	57.5	72.5	82.5	51.5
Fourth nymph	5	17.5	42.5	65	75	41
Average time effect	8	28	50.5	63	69.46	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	4.22		3.15		5.37	

Effect of *A. cymbiformis* fungal filtrate at 50% concentration on the corrected mortality rates of different nymphal stages of *A. fabae*

Table (4) shows the effects of *A. cymbiformis* fungal filtrate at a 50% concentration on the targeted stage and time periods, as well as the corrected *A. fabae* mortality percentages. The results showed significant differences in mortality rates depend on the stage effect. The first nymphal stage had the highest mortality rate of 71.2% compared to the other stages, with the

second, third, and fourth nymphal stages having mortality rates of 63.9%, 58.5%, and 55.4% respectively. In terms of time period effect, the 5-day period had much better than the other periods, with an adjusted mortality rate of 70.4%, compared to the 1, 2, 3, and 4-day periods, which provided corrected mortality rates of 19.2%, 41%, 57%, and 63.9%, respectively. Regarding the interaction impact, the first nymphal stage had a mortality rate of 95% after 5 days, exceeding the other nymphal stages. The mortality rate for the control treatment was 2.5% after 5 days.

Table 4. Effect of *A. cymbiformis* Fungal Filtrate at 50% Concentration on Corrected Mortality Percentages of Different Nymphal Stages of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	23.5	67.5	85	85	95	71.2
Second nymph	27.5	50	72.5	82	87.5	63.9
Third nymph	20	47.5	62.5	77.5	85	58.5
Fourth nymph	22.5	37.5	62.5	72.5	82	55.4
Average time effect	19.2	41	57	63.9	70.4	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	3.89		3.44		5.05	

Table 5 shows the effects of *A. cymbiformis* fungal filtrate at a 75% concentration on the targeted stage and time periods, as well as the corrected mortality percentages of *A. fabae*. The results indicated significant differences in mortality

rates based on the stage effect. The first nymphal stage had the highest death rate (79.7%), followed by the second nymphal stage (76%). The mortality rates for the third and fourth nymphal stages were 70.42% and 66.5%,

respectively. Regarding the time period effect, the 5-day period performed much better than the others, with an adjusted mortality rate of 75.96%. In comparison, the corrected mortality rates for the first, second, third, and fourth days were 24.5%, 54%, 67%, and 73.96%. In terms

on the interaction impact, the first nymphal stage had the highest mortality rate of 100% after 5 days, greatly outperforming the other nymphal stages. The control treatment resulted in a 3% death rate after five days.

Table 5. Effect of *A. cymbiformis* Fungal Filtrate at 75% Concentration on Corrected Mortality Percentages of Different Nymphal Stages of *A. fabae* After 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	40	70	90	97.5	100	79.7
Second nymph	37.5	65	87.5	95	95	76
Third nymph	22.5	65	82.5	89.8	92.3	70.42
Fourth nymph	22.5	70	70	82.5	87.5	66.5
Average time effect	24.5	54	67	73.96	75.96	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	4.61		4.03		6.23	

Figure 6. shows how the fungal filtrate of *A. cymbiformis* at a 100% concentration affects the adjusted mortality percentages of different developmental stages of *A. fabae* during time. The findings show considerable differences in mortality rates between the periods. The first nymph stage had the highest average mortality rate (82%), followed by the second nymph stage (79.46%). The third and fourth nymph stages had lower mortality rates (73.94% and 71%, respectively). Regarding the impact of time

period, the 4-day treatment duration had the highest average mortality rate of 77.5%, that exceeded the other durations. The corrected mortality rates for the 1, 2, and 3-day treatments were 26%, 55.44%, and 71.46%. In terms of interaction effects, the first nymph stage had the highest mortality rate of the study, which stood at 100% after four days. This was followed by the second, third, and fourth nymph stages, which had mortality rates of 97.5%, 95%, and 90% after 4 days

Table 6. Effect of *A. cymbiformis* Fungal Filtrate at 100% Concentration on Corrected Mortality Percentages of Different Nymphal Stages of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	40	75	95	100	100	82
Second nymph	40	70	89.8	97.5	100	79.46
Third nymph	25	67.2	85	95	97.5	73.94
Fourth nymph	25	65	82.5	90	92.5	71
Average time effect	26	55.44	71.46	77.5	79	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	4.08		3.22		5.71	

Table 7. shows how the fungal filtrate of *A. jodhpurensis* at a 25% concentration affects the adjusted mortality percentages of different

developmental stages of *A. fabae* over time. The statistics show considerable differences in mortality rates between the periods. The first

nymph stage had the greatest average mortality rate of 65.5%, followed by the second, third, and fourth stages at 59%, 48%, and 44.9%, respectively. In terms of the impact of time, the 4-day treatment duration had the greatest average mortality rate of 61%, exceeding the other durations. The corrected mortality rates

for the 1-, 2-, and 3-day treatments were 8%, 29.4%, and 50.5%. In terms of interaction effects, the first nymph stage had the highest mortality rate (95% after 4 days), exceeding the other nymph stages. After 5 days, the control treatment had a mortality rate of 1.5%.

Table 7. Effect of Fungal Filtrate of *A. jodhpurensis* at 25% Concentration in Corrected Percentages of Anaphylaxis of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 days of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	10	47.5	80	95	95	65.5
Second nymph	15	40	65	87.5	87.5	59
Third nymph	5	37.5	50	62.5	85	48
Fourth nymph	10	22	57.5	60	75	44.9
Average time effect	8	29.4	50.5	61	69.96	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	3.77		2.95		4.82	

able 8. shows the effect of a 50% concentration of *A. jodhpurensis* fungal filtrate on the target phase and time periods in *A. fabae* individuals' corrected mortality percentages. The results show significant differences in mortality rates based on the phase effect factor, with the first nymph stage having the highest mortality rate at 69.1% compared to the other stages, which had mortality rates of 62%, 56.5%, and 54% for the second, third, and fourth nymph stages, respectively. In terms of time period effect, the

5-day period performed much better than the other periods, with a mortality rate of 70.1% compared to the 1, 2, 3, and 4-day periods, which had corrected mortality percentages of 19.5%, 39.5%, 52.5%, and 62.5%, respectively. For the interaction effect, the first nymph stage had the highest mortality rate at 95.5% after 5 days, exceeding the other nymph stages. It is worth noting that the control treatment resulted in only 2.5% mortality after 5 days.

Table 8. Effect of Fungal Leachate of *A. jodhpurensis* at 50% Concentration on Corrected Mortality Percentages of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	30	62.5	75	82.5	95.5	69.1
Second nymph	22.5	47.5	67.5	85	87.5	62
Third nymph	22.5	45	57.5	72.5	85	56.5
Fourth nymph	20	40	60	70	80	54
Average time effect	19.5	39.5	52.5	62.5	70.1	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	4.38		3.78		5.24	

The table (9) shows the effects of fungal filtrate from the fungus *A. jodhpurensis* at a 75%

concentration on different developmental stages and time periods, expressed as corrected

mortality percentages for the *A. fabae*. The result revealed substantial differences in mortality rates according to the developmental stage factor. The first nymphal stage had the highest mortality rate of 77% compared to the other stages, with the second, third, and fourth nymphal stage having mortality rates of 72.5%, 67.7%, and 63%, respectively. In terms of time duration, the 5-day period exceeded the other durations, with a

mortality rate of 77.5%, as opposed to the 1, 2, 3, and 4-day durations, which had corrected mortality percentages of 20.5%, 48.2%, 64.5%, and 70.5%, respectively. In terms of the interaction impact, the first nymphal stage had the greatest mortality rate of 100% after 5 days, followed by the second nymphal stage at 97.5%, exceeding the other nymphal stages. The control treatment had a mortality rate of 1% after 5 days.

Table 9. Effect of Fungal Filtrate from *A. jodhpurensis* at a 75% Concentration on Corrected Mortality Percentages of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	32.5	67.5	87.5	97.5	100	77
Second nymph	35	65	77.5	87.5	97.5	72.5
Third nymph	20	56	82.5	85	95	67.7
Fourth nymph	15	52.5	75	82.5	90	63
Average time effect	20.5	48.2	64.5	70.5	77.5	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	3.46		3.69		5.66	

Table 10 shows the effects of a 100% concentration of fungal filtrate from on different stages of development and time periods, represented as corrected mortality percentages for the *A. fabae*. The results showed substantial differences in mortality rates depending on the developmental stage factor. The first nymphal stage had the highest mortality rate of 82.5%, followed by the second, third, and fourth nymphal stage at 78%, 74.6%, and 71.5%, respectively. In terms of time duration, the 4-day

period performed much better than the other durations, with a death rate of 77.5%, compared to the 1, 2, and 3-day durations, which had corrected mortality percentages of 27%, 54%, and 72.4%, respectively. In terms of the interaction impact, the first nymphal stage had the greatest death rate of 100% after four days, followed by the second and third nymphal stage at 97.5% and 95.5%, respectively. The control treatment reached 3% of mortality rate after five days.

Table 10. Effect of Fungal Filtrate from *A. jodhpurensis* at a 100% Concentration on Corrected Mortality Percentages of *A. fabae* after 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 Days of Treatment

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
First nymph	47.5	2	95	100	100	82.5
Second nymph	40	70	87.5	97.5	100	78
Third nymph	25	65	89.5	95.5	95.5	74.6
Fourth nymph	22.5	67.5	85	90	92.5	71.5
Average time effect	27	67.5	72.4	77.6	78.6	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	2.79		3.99		6.07	

The results of this study were consistent (Zinhom, 2020), who reported that the fungal filtrate of *B. bassiana* at a 100% concentration had 41.10% mortality rate in Khapra beetle larvae. The larvae showed symptoms of poisoning, such as reduced mobility, lethargy, and decreased consuming, before death. This result is agreed with the results of Al-Shuwaili and Jaber (2010), who determined that fungal filtrates of *Cladosporium oxysporum* and *B. bassiana* at 100% concentration significantly caused mortality rates of 55.5% and 52.17%, respectively, in the nymphal stage of the *A. fabae*. Toxins produced by fungi can enter the insect's body through the mouth, respiratory apertures, or contact with the insect's surface, causing poisoning symptoms to occur (Samson et al., 1988). Ghisalberti et al. (1990) also reported that *T. harzianum* can produce harmful metabolic chemicals such as pyrone and 6-pentyl pyrone. Furthermore, (Khalaf, 2011) noticed that spraying fungal filtrate is more effective than using it as bait. This could be because the filtrate enters the insect's

digestive tract and is exposed to digestive enzymes, reducing its efficacy. However, because the fungal filtrate contains poisonous metabolic components, it immediately impacts the insect and is thus more efficient and effective than bait.

Effect of Fungal Filtrate from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* on the Productivity of Adult *A. fabae*

Table 11. shows the average number of new individuals produced by adult *A. fabae* when exposed to a 75% concentration of fungal filtrate from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis*. The results showed a significant decrease in productivity among adults. The average number of nymphs produced by *A. fabae* adults using a 75% concentration of fungal filtrate from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* was 1.64 and 1.7 nymphs /female, respectively, compared to the control treatment, which produced an average of 3.82 nymphs/female after 5 days.

Table 11. Effect of Fungal Filtrate from *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* at a 75% Concentration on the Productivity of Adult *A. fabae*

Stage	Mortality percentage period (Days)					Average effect of concentration
	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>A.cymbiformis</i>	2.3	1.9	1.7	1.4	0.9	1.64
<i>A. jodhpurensis</i>	2.3	2	1.9	1.4	0.9	1.7
Control	3.6	3.8	3.9	3.8	4	3.82
Duration effect rate	2.73	2.56	2.5	2.2	1.9	
L.S.D	Concentration effect		Time		Interaction	
0.05	0.71		0.58		0.88	

This result is consistent with Al-Hattab and Mohammed. (2008), who reported that the fungal filtrate of *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* at a 75% concentration significantly reduced the productivity of adult green peach aphids, with average production rates of 8.33 and 4.00 nymphs/female, respectively, compared to the control treatment, which had 21 nymphs/female. The results of this study were consistent the study of Hatim and Basim. (2020), who found that treating adult green peach aphids with *T. harzianum* filtrate reduced

their productivity. He also realized that raising the concentration of the filtrate reduced productivity even more, with 17 nymphs/female at a 100% concentration of the fungal filtrate vs 28.33 nymphs/female in the control condition. The decrease in productivity may be attributed to the fungi's production of certain enzymes, as clarified by Ito et al. (2007), who determined that *B. bassiana* produces extracellular proteases in liquid media, which significantly impacted legume insects, with a 91% mortality rate 7 days after treatment. Furthermore, Al-Jubouri (2007)

emphasized the impact of *Cladosporium oxysporum* and influence on the oleander insect, explaining the fungus' ability to create the enzymes chitinase and lipase, as well as toxins that allow it to infiltrate the host's body.

Conclusion

The fungal filtrate from entomopathogenic fungi, *A. cymbiformis* and *A. jodhpurensis* showed potential against all developmental stages of *A. fabae* under laboratory conditions. As well, reductions in total fecundity of the treated adult insect pests were also recorded. However, further studies are required to confirm the efficacy of fungal filtrates of both fungal species under greenhouse and field conditions. In addition, the potential effects of fungal filtrates of both fungal species in combination with other control methods are also required to be evaluated.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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